

Supplemental Data Table 1

Gene Symbol	Gene Name	Fold Regulation	p-value
Gys2	Glycogen synthase 2	8.91	0.334977
Pdp2	Pyruvate dehydrogenase phosphatase catalytic subunit 2	8.85	0.301455
Pgk2	Phosphoglycerate kinase 2	7.79	0.314370
Eno2	Enolase 2, gamma neuronal	7.39	0.262535
Prps111	Phosphoribosyl pyrophosphate synthetase 1-like 1	7.29	0.302196
Gck	Glucokinase	6.25	0.249568
Fbp1	Fructose bisphosphatase 1	5.74	0.220575
G6pc	Glucose-6-phosphatase, catalytic	5.29	0.271691
Phkg1	Phosphorylase kinase gamma 1	4.55	0.297965
Aldob	Aldolase B, fructose-bisphosphate	4.39	0.314192
Sdhb	Succinate dehydrogenase complex, subunit D, integral membrane protein	4.31	0.174693
Pklr	Pyruvate kinase liver and red blood cell	4.14	0.214494
Cs	Citrate synthase	4.12	0.273991
Idh1	Isocitrate dehydrogenase 1 (NADP+), soluble	3.99	0.085887
Phka1	Phosphorylase kinase alpha 1	3.96	0.138223
Hk2	Hexokinase 2	3.94	0.289335
Pdpr	Pyruvate dehydrogenase phosphatase regulatory subunit	3.69	0.054357
Pgm1	Phosphoglucomutase 1	3.43	0.025623
Gbe1	Glucan (1,4-alpha-), branching enzyme 1	3.32	0.122000
Galm	Galactose mutarotase	3.26	0.281518
H6pd	Hexose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (glucose 1-dehydrogenase)	3.14	0.179843
Phkb	Phosphorylase kinase beta	3.11	0.290661
Suclg2	Succinate-Coenzyme A ligase, GDP-forming, beta subunit	3.06	0.167221
Gsk3b	Glycogen synthase kinase 3 beta	2.89	0.071240
G6pc3	Glucose 6 phosphatase, catalytic, 3	2.85	0.196634
Ogdh	Oxoglutarate dehydrogenase (lipoamide)	2.80	0.054121
Sdha	Succinate dehydrogenase complex, subunit A, flavoprotein (Fp)	2.67	0.103829
Ag1	Amylo-1,6-glucosidase, 4-alpha-glucanotransferase	2.58	0.340325
Fbp2	Fructose bisphosphatase 2	2.58	0.354920
Rpe	Ribulose-5-phosphate-3-epimerase	2.57	0.086863
G6pdx	Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase X-linked	2.52	0.099955
Gapdhs	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase, spermatogenic	2.51	0.153213
Pdk4	Pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase, isoenzyme 4	2.46	0.346032
Pcx	Pyruvate carboxylase	2.45	0.164928
Pck1	Phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase 1, cytosolic	2.39	0.222352
Aco1	Aconitase 1	2.27	0.310534
Tpi1	Triosephosphate isomerase 1	2.22	0.107150
Acly	ATP citrate lyase	2.12	0.100459
Idh3a	Isocitrate dehydrogenase 3 (NAD+) alpha	2.10	0.217655
Pdk1	Pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase, isoenzyme 1	2.03	0.329138
Eno1	Enolase 1, alpha non-neuron	1.96	0.291738

Dlst	Dihydrolipoamide S-succinyltransferase (E2 component of 2-oxo-glutarate complex)	1.95	0.109057
Phkg2	Phosphorylase kinase, gamma 2 (testis)	1.92	0.099304
Gapdh	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase	1.88	0.351087
Idh3b	Isocitrate dehydrogenase 3 (NAD+) beta	1.87	0.084510
Sdhc	Succinate dehydrogenase complex, subunit C, integral membrane protein	1.86	0.122557
Pgm2	Phosphoglucomutase 2	1.83	0.092464
Pdha1	Pyruvate dehydrogenase E1 alpha 1	1.79	0.022987
Actb	Actin, beta	1.75	0.192635
Gsk3a	Glycogen synthase kinase 3 alpha	1.69	0.048652
Pdk2	Pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase, isoenzyme 2	1.65	0.205488
Pygm	Muscle glycogen phosphorylase	1.64	0.336075
Rpia	Ribose 5-phosphate isomerase A	1.64	0.106883
Gpi1	Glucose phosphate isomerase 1	1.57	0.021753
Bpgm	2,3-bisphosphoglycerate mutase	1.52	0.318244
Mdh1b	Malate dehydrogenase 1B, NAD (soluble)	1.51	0.234145
Pygl	Liver glycogen phosphorylase	1.51	0.369474
Hk3	Hexokinase 3	1.48	0.869584
Sdhb	Succinate dehydrogenase complex, subunit B, iron sulfur (lp)	1.48	0.189077
Did	Dihydrolipoamide dehydrogenase	1.41	0.234521
Prps1	Phosphoribosyl pyrophosphate synthetase 1	1.41	0.186816
Fh1	Fumarate hydratase 1	1.38	0.389808
Pfkl	Phosphofructokinase, liver, B-type	1.37	0.438286
Prps2	Phosphoribosyl pyrophosphate synthetase 2	1.36	0.358640
Aldoc	Aldolase C, fructose-bisphosphate	1.33	0.458853
Pdhb	Pyruvate dehydrogenase (lipoamide) beta	1.32	0.266584
Idh2	Isocitrate dehydrogenase 2 (NADP+), mitochondrial	1.26	0.404460
Ugp2	UDP-glucose pyrophosphorylase 2	1.25	0.191696
Taldo1	Transaldolase 1	1.21	0.517486
Dlat	Dihydrolipoamide S-acetyltransferase (E2 component of pyruvate dehydrogenase complex)	1.19	0.705631
Suclg1	Succinate-CoA ligase, GDP-forming, alpha subunit	1.17	0.487691
Idh3g	Isocitrate dehydrogenase 3 (NAD+), gamma	1.15	0.585675
Pgm3	Phosphoglucomutase 3	1.14	0.588506
Pck2	Phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase 2 (mitochondrial)	1.12	0.627267
Hsp90ab1	Heat shock protein 90 alpha (cytosolic), class B member 1	1.11	0.765239
Tkt	Transketolase	1.03	0.851994
Rbks	Ribokinase	1.02	0.861766
Aldoa	Aldolase A, fructose-bisphosphate	-1.01	0.939456
Mdh2	Malate dehydrogenase 2, NAD (mitochondrial)	-1.04	0.949860
Pdk3	Pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase, isoenzyme 3	-1.04	0.922465
Aco2	Aconitase 2, mitochondrial	-1.09	0.541878
Pgk1	Phosphoglycerate kinase 1	-1.11	0.788113
Mdh1	Malate dehydrogenase 1, NAD (soluble)	-1.14	0.595900
Gys1	Glycogen synthase 1, muscle	-1.16	0.537754
Pgam2	Phosphoglycerate mutase 2	-1.20	0.451400
Sucla2	Succinate-Coenzyme A ligase, ADP-forming, beta subunit	-1.34	0.484608

Eno3	Enolase 3, beta muscle	-1.49	0.121249
B2m	Beta-2 microglobulin	-1.84	0.199476
Gusb	Glucuronidase, beta	-1.97	0.432224